

Futures Thinking among European Pre-service and In-service Teachers

Xinlan Zhang, Iina Hyyppä, Ilona Södervik, Heidi Krzywacki, Ali Soroshzadeh & Antti Laherto

University of Helsinki, Finland

Correspondence: xinlan.zhang@helsinki.fi

How to cite: Zhang, X., Hyyppä, I., Södervik, I., Krzywacki, H., Soroshzadeh, A., & Laherto, A. (2026). Futures Thinking among European Pre-service and In-service Teachers. Erasmus+ Teacher Academy “Teacher Education for a Future in Flux” (*teff*). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20146591>

1. Introduction

Education has been called upon to remedy the global crises and change the trajectory of the future of humanity towards a more sustainable direction (UNESCO, 2021). Given the complexity of future challenges (OECD, 2019; UNESCO, 2021), it is necessary for educational systems across Europe to prepare future generations not only with knowledge and skills but also with the capacity to anticipate and influence the future (Voogt & Roblin, 2012; OECD, 2019). Therefore, teacher education needs to equip teachers with future-oriented mindsets and skills to enable them to respond and adapt to transformations, but also initiate them, and in turn enable their students to do so (Laherto et al., 2026).

Research has shown that teachers have difficulty imagining different futures – especially futures based on their own hopes and futures with societal transformations and significant diversions from current trends and structures (e.g., Hyyppä et al., 2024; 2025; Rasa et al., 2024; Varpanen et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2026). Therefore, it is important to understand and be able to foster their futures thinking and agency.

This article reports on research within the Erasmus+ Teacher Academy “Teacher Education for a Future in Flux” (*teff*) project, adopting a multi-method approach to understanding pre-service and in-service teachers’ futures thinking with the operationalised concept of futures consciousness (Ahvenharju et al., 2018). In addition, the study explores similarities and differences in teachers’ futures consciousness across different European countries. Teachers’ futures consciousness is also elaborated by their year of study (in teacher education) and teaching experience.

The study provides research-based foundations for the *teff* White Paper “Teachers as Drivers of Change? Recommendations for Future-oriented Teacher Education” (Laherto et al., 2026). Taken together, this work suggests implications for future-oriented teacher education aiming to support teachers’ ability to imagine alternative futures of schooling and to strengthen their professional agency and adaptive expertise.

2. Theoretical framework: Teachers’ Futures Thinking

Futures thinking, as conceptualised in the field of Futures Studies, refers to ways of understanding, imagining, and critically engaging with multiple possible futures to reflect on

how present actions shape what lies ahead (Miller, 2015; Ahvenharju et al., 2018). Rather than predicting what will happen, futures thinking emphasises anticipation, alternative pathways, and purposeful choice under conditions of uncertainty. While competence in futures thinking has been acknowledged as an important educational objective (UNESCO, 2021, Miller, 2018; Poli, 2021), and teachers play a key role in fostering students' mindsets, teachers' own ways of thinking about the future have remained an under-investigated topic (Varpanen et al., 2022; Vidergor, 2023).

Several models have been suggested in the Futures Studies literature to operationalize research on futures thinking. The research reported here employs the Futures Consciousness model (Ahvenharju et al., 2018, 2021) and adapts it to the context of education and the profession of teaching. The model was chosen because its five dimensions have clear connections to teachers' work.

The dimension of **Agency Beliefs** concerns how individuals understand their capacity – together with others – to influence what emerges over time (Ahvenharju et al., 2018). In the context of this study, it connects to the temporal element in teachers' professional agency (Varpanen et al., 2022). The dimension of **Systems Perceptions** relates to recognizing interdependencies, feedback loops, and cause–effect relations across social structures (Ahvenharju et al., 2018). Research suggests that engaging with futures-oriented tasks can strengthen teachers' attention to complexity and interconnectedness (Hyyppä et al., 2024). The dimension of **Concern for Others** focuses on caring beyond one's immediate self-interest, extending ethical responsibility across people, places, and generations (Ahvenharju et al., 2018). In teaching, this forward-looking care often motivates long-term commitments to students and society (O'Connor, 2008; Sund & Wickman, 2008). The dimension of **Time Perspectives** describes how individuals relate past experiences, present actions, and long-term futures (Ahvenharju et al., 2018). While teacher education frequently addresses future orientation through career planning, broader reflection on the future of schooling itself is comparatively rare (Eren, 2012; Lombardo, 2014). The dimension of **Openness to Alternatives** involves accepting uncertainty and acknowledging that multiple, unforeseen futures remain possible (Ahvenharju et al., 2018; Miller, 2015). For teachers, this aligns with adaptive expertise and growth-oriented thinking in the profession, yet engagement with radical or systemic future change is still underexplored (van Tartwijk et al., 2017).

3. Methods

3.1 Futures thinking activity

In 2023, the *teff* team at the University of Helsinki (UH) developed a Futures Thinking Activity (FTA) to understand European teachers' futures thinking regarding teaching profession in a comprehensive manner, involving both qualitative and quantitative approaches.

Participants were encouraged to reflect on their conceptions of the future of the teacher's profession by completing two short essay tasks and responding to a multiple-choice questionnaire with survey statements on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from “fully disagree” to “fully agree”.

The two writing tasks were a **futures visioning** task, 1, followed by a **backcasting** task, 2:

Task 1. 'It is the year 2050 and you work as a teacher. Write a short story on your workday in your desired future. You may discuss, for example, working methods and environments, pedagogical solutions, pupils and students, interaction, potential conflicts, and the role of school in society.'

Task 2. 'Now imagine yourself in the desired future you described above. Look back towards the present day and briefly describe the development and changes that have occurred on the way to this future. Also consider what or who has influenced the changes.'

After these writing assignments, participants responded to three statements on their experiences with the writing tasks, another three statements on their overall perceptions of their futures thinking, and 27 statements (Teacher Futures Consciousness questionnaire) reflecting their futures thinking as teachers across five dimensions: Time Perspective, Agency Beliefs, Openness to Alternatives, Systems Perceptions, and Responsibility. The Teacher Futures Consciousness (TFC) survey was developed by the UH team, inspired by the Futures Consciousness (FC) questionnaire by Ahvenharju et al. (2018, 2021). To ensure that participants clearly understood the questionnaire and responded accurately to it, the whole TFC survey was translated into their local native language with the support of project partners. At the end of the activity, participants were introduced to various forms of futures and futures thinking frameworks through a short lecture and a learning material, the Futures Thinking tool (Hyyppä et al., 2026).

A draft of the short essay prompts and the TFC statements was reviewed and commented on by *teff* partners. Before the main study, a pilot test was conducted with 10 participants, including university students and staff from the Faculty of Educational Sciences at the UH, who did not have any background in futures thinking. The purpose of the pilot was to check whether the questionnaire was clear and easy to understand. Based on the pilot results, modifications were made to the instrument. In the qualitative section, additional guidance was added to the prompts to help participants focus on the future of the teaching profession. In the quantitative section, some items were removed, including items where all participants gave the same response (e.g., all 1 or all 5), items with overlapping content, and items that had not been stated clearly. The final version of the quantitative TFC scale included 27 items (Zhang et al., 2026).

3.2 Data collection

Data collection took place from autumn 2023 until spring 2026. All participants were enrolled at or collaborated with partner institutions involved in the *teff* project. Participants at the undergraduate and master's levels were reached with the assistance of local university representatives, teacher educators, and researchers. The Futures Thinking activities were carried out either as part of their teacher education courses or as stand-alone sessions in online, face-to-face, or hybrid formats.

During these activities, participants completed an online questionnaire and engaged in futures thinking discussions. The specific data collection context for each country is described below,

followed by Table 1, which provides an overview of the valid data collected in each country, including the distribution of pre-service and in-service teachers:

- Finland
 - A total of 342 pre-service teachers from Finland participated in this study during a futures thinking activity. Data were collected in October 2023 and October 2025 as part of a mandatory first-year online course for bachelor's students in the education programme at the University of Helsinki. The course was taught by the same lecturer, but the data came from two different student cohorts;
 - 25 in-service teachers' data were collected from local schools, teacher training schools, and personal networks by *teff* partners in the UH team.
- Germany
 - A total of 71 pre-service teachers' data were collected by *teff* project partners at the University of Cologne in 2024 and 2026, involving students enrolled in educational sciences programmes at the University of Cologne;
 - 7 in-service teachers' data were collected in local schools by *teff* partners at the University of Cologne.
- Belgium
 - 29 pre-service teachers' data were collected from students in the Educational Master's programme at KU Leuven through an online Futures Thinking Activity organised by *teff* partners;
 - 3 in-service teachers' data were collected in person from a Futures Thinking Activity-based social event organised by *teff* partners at KU Leuven. All questionnaires were completed with pen and paper, then transferred into digital form.
- Italy
 - 2 pre-service teachers' data from University of Florence was collected as after-course assignment taught by a *teff* partner;
 - 31 pre-service teachers' data were collected from University of Bologna during a Futures Thinking Activity organised by a *teff* partner in the UH team during an academic visit.
- Sweden
 - 2 in-service teachers' data were collected through a series of teacher training activities organised by a *teff* partner from Linnaeus University, where participants completed the questionnaire as an assignment following the training sessions.
- Lithuania
 - A total of 13 in-service teachers' data were collected as a part of an in-service teacher education course on citizenship education by a *teff* partner from the UH team.

Table 1. Overview of valid data collection for WP9 D9.3.

Country	Institution	Participants	
		Pre-service teachers	In-service teachers
Finland	University of Helsinki	179 (2023); 163 (2025)	25
Germany	University of Cologne	70 (2024); 1 (2026)	7
Belgium	KU Leuven	29	3
Italy	University of Florence	2	-
	University of Bologna	31	-
Sweden	Linnaeus University	-	2
Lithuania	University of Helsinki	-	13
In total	525	475	50

All participants were informed of the main aim of the study before data collection and voluntarily consented to the use of their data for research purposes. They also agreed to be contacted for a follow-up interview if necessary. A privacy policy document was also embedded at the beginning of the survey.

Throughout the project, *teff* partners have made considerable efforts to reach in-service teachers across Europe to participate in the Futures Thinking Activity. Due to the time requirements of the activity, only a limited amount of data was collected from in-service teachers. Therefore, in the analysis, the data from pre-service teachers across Europe is emphasised, while lightly addressing in-service teachers' views.

3.3 Data analysis

In earlier research, qualitative methods such as narrative inquiry have proven to be powerful in analysing teachers' writing about the future (e.g., Varpanen et al., 2022; Hyppä et al., 2024; 2025; 2026a). In addition, research and development of teacher education needs quantitative, validated instruments on teachers' futures thinking. Therefore, as part of the Futures Thinking Activity, the Teacher Futures Consciousness (TFC) scale was developed and modified based on the Futures Consciousness framework and model (Ahvenharju et al., 2018), originally devised within the fields of psychology and future studies as a non-context-specific framework. In *teff*, the model was specifically contextualised for teacher education.

3.3.1 Quantitative analysis

The initial version of the TFC scale included five dimensions, consistent with the original FC scale: Time Perspective, Agency Beliefs, Openness to Alternatives, Systems Perception, and Responsibility (referred to as Concern for Others in the FC scale). A contextualised instrument was validated (Zhang et al., 2026) and four dimensions emerged, instead of five. Two dimensions within the initial TFC model - Time Perspective and Openness to Alternatives – emerged as one single dimension.

Teacher's Sense of Responsibility (5 items) connects individual-level care for students with an understanding of the role of schools, then extends to broader social and sustainability concerns (Zhang et al., 2026); **Teacher's Openness to Futures** (4 items) reflects teachers' willingness to think about and envision multiple possible futures for the teaching profession

and schooling, functioning as a motivational disposition role in fostering teacher's agency (Zhang et al., 2026); **Teacher's Agency Beliefs** (4 items) captures various perspectives of teacher's professional agency, including their perceived ability to influence their own work, professional development, school community, and the broader education system (Zhang et al., 2026); **Teacher's Systemic Awareness** (4 items), expresses teachers' interpretation of how the education system develops, including the role of curricula, the impact of social change, the historical context of education, and how these understandings help them anticipate future trends (Zhang et al., 2026).

In this article, Teachers' Futures Consciousness between the countries, first-year and non-first-year students, and teachers with and without teaching experience were described and compared. The descriptive statistics, independent samples t-tests, and Welch ANOVA were analysed with SPSS 31.0.

3.3.2 Qualitative analysis

The short essay written tasks – futures visioning (task 1) and backcasting (task 2) – were analysed through a narrative inquiry analysis as in Lutovac and Kaasila (2014). A deductive approach was taken in searching for manifestations of the dimensions of Teachers' Futures Consciousness: Teacher's Sense of Responsibility, Teacher's Openness to Futures, Teacher's Agency Beliefs, and Teacher's Systemic Awareness. The definitions of the dimensions followed the categorisations of the scale validation presented above.

The analysis also examined the differences in the manifestations of the dimensions of Teachers' Futures Consciousness across the two tasks. To understand the role of the tasks and their prompts in pre-service teachers' futures consciousness, the analysis explored the emphasis of each dimension in the futures visioning (task 1) and in the backcasting (task 2). For the qualitative analysis, only the data from pre-service teachers were used.

4. Results

4.1 TFC statistical results

In the *teff* project, pre-service and in-service teachers' data were collected from six European countries. According to the background questions for the overall perceptions of futures thinking, most of the European pre-service teachers had thought a lot about their future ($M = 4.09$, $SD = 0.91$). However, the difficulty of thinking about the future varied among the participants, even though the average score was fairly neutral ($M = 2.91$, $SD = 1.09$). Their responses towards whether a future teaching career aligned with their personal expectations were relatively neutral ($M = 3.09$, $SD = 1.05$), indicating a degree of uncertainty in their future profession visioning (see Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of European pre-service teachers' overall perceptions of futures thinking.

	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Min	Max
I think a lot about my own future.	475	4.09	0.91	1	5
I find it difficult to imagine how things could be different in the future than today.	475	2.91	1.091	1	5
I believe that the teacher's profession in the future will follow my desires.	475	3.09	1.046	1	5

In the Teacher Futures Consciousness model (see Table 3), **Teacher's Sense of Responsibility** showed the highest mean score ($M = 4.22$, $SD = 0.52$), suggesting a consistent tendency among European pre-service teachers to emphasise the importance of responsibility in their teaching profession. In contrast, **Teacher's Openness to Futures** received the lowest mean score ($M = 3.59$, $SD = 0.78$), indicating a lower tendency to envision their future professional development. At the same time, a high level of individual differences was observed.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the four dimensions forming the TFC scale in the *teff* pre-service teachers' sample.

TFC Dimensions	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Min	Max
Teacher's Sense of Responsibility (TSR)	475	4.22	0.52	2.20	5.00
Teacher's Openness to Futures (TOF)	475	3.50	0.78	1.00	5.00
Teacher's Agency Beliefs (TAB)	475	3.75	0.59	2.00	5.00
Teacher's Systemic Awareness (TSA)	475	3.65	0.61	1.00	5.00

4.1.2 Pre-service Teachers' Futures Consciousness in each country

After reviewing the general descriptive statistics of Teachers' Futures Consciousness, we now focus on the pre-service teachers' futures thinking across different countries. Since the samples from each country are independent, the overall TFC scores are combined for further comparison and reference.

Based on the samples of pre-service teachers from Finland, Germany, Belgium, and Italy, there are some noticeable differences in teachers' future consciousness (See Table 4). Among these countries, **Finland** has the highest overall mean score ($M = 3.86$, $SD = 0.44$), while pre-service teachers from Belgium have a relatively lower score ($M = 3.53$, $SD = 0.41$). However, due to the relatively small sample sizes in some countries and the imbalanced data across groups, the results only provide an initial overview of how futures consciousness is reflected in these national samples, but cannot be taken as fully representative of pre-service teachers in each country.

Looking into the TFC dimensions, pre-service teachers across all countries had consistently high and stable scores in **Teacher's Sense of Responsibility (TSR)**. This suggests that European

pre-service teachers already demonstrate a strong sense of responsibility before they officially begin their teaching profession. The consistency of this pattern across countries also indicates that responsibility may be a shared characteristic of pre-service teachers across different cultural contexts.

However, pre-service teachers from Finland had the highest scores in **Teacher's Openness to Futures (TOF)** ($M = 3.59, SD = 0.77$) and **Teacher's Agency Beliefs (TAB)** ($M = 3.86, SD = 0.53$). This may be related to the strong emphasis placed on fostering autonomy in Finnish teacher education, which encourages pre-service teachers to take an active role in their professional development.

Table 4. Comparison of TFC and its dimensions across countries (means, standard deviations, and Welch ANOVA results)

TFC & Dimensions	Finland ($N = 342$)		Germany ($N = 71$)		Belgium ($N = 29$)		Italy ($N = 33$)		F	P
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
TFC	3.86	0.44	3.57	0.36	3.53	0.41	3.66	0.43	16.02	<0.001
TSR	4.27	0.51	3.99	0.51	4.09	0.47	4.28	0.62	6.76	<0.001
TOF	3.59	0.77	3.44	0.71	3.11	0.80	3.07	0.78	7.4	<0.001
TAB	3.86	0.53	3.48	0.62	3.28	0.67	3.55	0.65	14.92	<0.001
TSA	3.71	0.61	3.36	0.60	3.63	0.52	3.74	0.50	6.61	<0.001

In order to further understand these differences, and given the significant imbalance in sample sizes across those countries, Welch ANOVA was employed to test the differences between countries (see Table 3).

The results show significant difference in TFC between different countries ($F(3, 73.55) = 16.02, p < 0.001$). Further Games-Howell post-hoc comparison tests showed that **Finland** was significantly higher than Germany ($p < 0.001$) and Belgium ($p = 0.001$) in TFC, while there was no significant difference with Italy ($p = 0.073$). Among the four TFC dimensions, the most significant difference was observed in **Teacher's Agency Beliefs (TAB)** ($F(3, 69.42) = 14.92, p < 0.001$). However, due to the imbalanced sample sizes of each country, the findings should be considered as indicative trends.

4.1.3 Teachers' Futures Consciousness in different groups

Independent samples t-tests were conducted to compare pre-service teachers' Futures Consciousness by their year of study and teaching experience.

To examine whether there are differences in futures thinking across year of study among European pre-service teachers, we divided the samples into two groups based on their year of study: first-year students ($N = 246$) and non-first-year students ($N = 229$). An independent-samples t-test was conducted (see Table 5).

The results showed that the two groups differed significantly on three dimensions: **Teacher's Sense of Responsibility (TSR)**, **Teacher's Openness to Futures (TOF)**, and **Teacher's Agency Beliefs (TAB)** ($p < 0.05$). On these dimensions, first-year pre-service teachers scored higher than non-first-year students (TSR: $t = 2.155$, $p = 0.033$; TOF: $t = 2.145$, $p = 0.032$; TAB: $t = 2.836$, $p = 0.005$), indicating pre-service teachers in their earlier year of teacher training show more concern about their students, school, and society; tend to be more open to their future profession; and show stronger intentions to be change makers in their future career compared to those who are further advanced in their studies. In contrast, no significant difference was found for Teacher's Systemic Awareness (TSA) ($t = 1.224$, $p = 0.222$).

Furthermore, the effect sizes across dimensions were generally small (Cohen's $d = 0.11$ – 0.26), indicating that although some differences were statistically significant, their practical impact was relatively limited (Cohen, 2013).

Table 5. Comparison of TFC across student grade levels (independent-samples t-test).

TFC Dimension	1st year	Non- 1st	1st year	Non- 1st	1st year	Non- 1st	t	Sig.(p)	Cohen's d
	N	N	M	M	SD	SD			
TSR	246	229	4.27	4.167	0.51	0.54	2.155	0.032	0.198
TOF	246	229	3.58	3.43	0.77	0.78	2.145	0.032	0.197
TAB	246	229	3.82	3.67	0.59	0.59	2.836	0.005	0.26
TSA	246	229	3.69	3.62	0.59	0.62	1.224	0.222	0.112

Teaching experience plays a crucial role in developing teachers' futures thinking and should not be overlooked (Zhang et al., 2026). Therefore, we conducted a comparison based on participants' teaching experience. As mentioned earlier, in addition to pre-service teachers, we also managed to collect a small amount of data from in-service teachers. In-service data were incorporated into the analysis and combined with the pre-service teacher sample for the "Teaching Experience" comparison ($N = 525$).

Participants were divided into two groups: teachers (pre- and in-service) with no teaching experience ($N = 192$, 36.6%) and those with teaching experience ($N = 333$, 63.4%). Based on this grouping, differences in future orientation were examined using independent samples t-tests.

The results showed that the two groups differed significantly on the **Teacher's Openness to Futures (TOF)** and **Teacher's Agency Beliefs (TAB)** dimensions ($p < 0.05$) (see Table 6). Specifically, participants with teaching experience (including both pre-service and in-service teachers) scored higher on these dimensions than pre-service teachers without any teaching experience (TOF: $t = -2.57$, $p = 0.010$; TAB: $t = -1.98$, $p = 0.048$). No significant differences were found in the other dimensions. Further analysis indicated that the effect sizes across all dimensions were relatively small (Cohen's $d < 0.30$).

Table 6. Comparison of TFC by different teaching experiences (independent-samples t-test)

TFC Dimension	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	<i>t</i>	Sig.(<i>p</i>)	Cohen's <i>d</i>
	<i>N</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SD</i>			
TSR	192	333	4.23	4.19	0.55	0.52	.827	0.409	0.075
TOF	192	333	3.40	3.58	0.83	0.73	-2.57	0.01	0.233
TAB	192	333	3.68	3.78	0.58	0.60	-1.983	0.048	0.180
TSA	192	333	3.63	3.69	0.67	0.56	-.962	0.337	0.087

4.2 TFC in Future Visioning and Backcasting tasks

The qualitative data was analysed through a narrative inquiry to gain a more in-depth understanding of how teachers' futures consciousness is manifested. First, the manifestations of TFC are explored by dimension. Second, they are explored by task (the futures visioning task 1 and the backcasting task 2).

4.2.1. Manifestations of TFC Dimensions

Teacher's Sense of Responsibility is manifested through efforts to address social barriers and inequities and to shape schools as safe spaces. Teacher's sense of responsibility is associated with building equitable school communities that bridge cultural differences and support inclusive, pluralistic ways of learning. Teachers view schools as connecting diverse groups: *"Students will come from many different cultures, and I hope that the school will succeed in building links between them."* [Pre-service teacher, Finland]

Teacher responsibility is also associated with mutual respect, fostering collaborative relationships with parents, creating accessible opportunities for participation, and contributing to the development of pluralistic and multicultural ways of living together through everyday pedagogical practices: *"There is a strong sense of mutual respect within the class, and cooperation between parents and teachers has also improved; there are many opportunities to get involved and fewer obligations."* [Pre-service teacher, Germany]

Teacher's Openness to Futures is evident in pre-service teachers' future visions through their understandings of change, professional agency, and uncertainty. Some emphasise the need for adaptability and continuous learning in response to a changing world: *"After more than 25 years, the world and the students will have changed and I would like to be informed even then, so that I can keep up with things."* [Pre-service teacher, Finland]

Teacher's openness to futures is associated with both uncertainty and hope, as well as a willingness to engage with ongoing change at the personal and systemic levels. Teachers articulate more transformative and long-term imaginaries of education, portraying the future as open and shaped by human agency: *"The transformation toward the future in 2050 was marked by a profound shift in the educational landscape. [...] This paradigm shift was driven*

largely by a new generation of dedicated educators who developed a holistic approach to education.” [Pre-service teacher, Germany]

Teacher’s Agency Beliefs are manifested in how pre-service teachers understand teachers as capable actors in their work. Teacher agency is often seen as being dependent on the structural, political, and technological conditions shaping future education: *“Teachers should have the freedom to decide how to structure their lessons, but there must be clear guidelines to make this possible [...]. I believe that the risk of making curriculum objectives too broad and vague – and thereby expanding teachers’ freedom excessively – could be detrimental to the future.”* [Pre-service teacher, Belgium]

Teacher’s agency beliefs are manifested through professional responsibility and awareness of conditions that enable or constrain their capacity to influence educational futures. Teachers’ agency is associated with hope for educators to be actively involved in shaping pedagogical technologies: *“...Breaking down the language barrier will certainly be influenced by technological pedagogical developments, so I hope that educators will be involved in thinking about what kind of tools are needed.”* [Pre-service teacher, Finland]

Teacher’s Systemic Awareness is manifested through reflections on the interconnections between schools and society, and through considering systems of change and the actors involved in shaping future schooling. This awareness is particularly expressed in relation to socioecological systems: *“[We have increased] understanding of the important connections between humans and nature.”* [Pre-service teacher, Finland]

Teachers reflect systemic awareness in teaching as understanding education as being embedded in social, cultural, ecological, and global systems, where teaching practices contribute to change beyond the classroom. Teachers emphasise how learning is shaped through global interconnectedness, cultural exchange, and transnational relationships within educational systems: *“Students are increasingly collaborating with others around the world, which helps them learn about different cultures.”* [Pre-service teacher, Belgium]

4.2.2. TFC Dimensions in Future Visioning and Backcasting tasks

The narrative inquiry analysis was also used to explore how each dimension of TFC is manifested in the two tasks, the futures visioning task 1 and the backcasting task 2. The units presented in Fig. 1 indicate coded text passages as elaborated in 4.2.1., and their frequencies in each of the two tasks.

The futures visioning task 1 has most manifestations of Teacher’s Sense of Responsibility and Teacher’s Openness to Futures. With a more substantial difference in distribution among the two tasks, Task 2 showed more manifestations of Teacher’s Systemic Awareness and Teacher’s Agency Beliefs. In other words, without the additional backcasting task, pre-service teachers’ manifestations of Teacher’s Systemic Awareness and Teacher’s Agency Beliefs remain notably more minimal.

Figure 1. Manifestations of TFC in Tasks 1 & 2.

5. Discussion

5.1 Discussion of the main findings

This article presents the research results regarding the Futures Thinking Activity and data collection that has been conducted within the *teff* project, employing a multi-method analytical approach to explore the dimensions of teachers' futures consciousness among European pre-service and in-service teachers, as well as the differences in these dimensions between teacher students in the early stages of their studies and those who are further along in their studies. In addition, the study compared the differences in these dimensions between those with no teaching experience and those who already have experience, within a sample consisting of teachers and teacher students.

Based on the Teacher Futures Consciousness scale (Zhang et al., 2026), pre-service teachers across EU displayed a shared value of responsibility as future teachers. Notably, according to the descriptives and country comparisons for TFC, Finnish pre-service teachers stood out on Teacher's Openness to Futures and Teacher's Agency Beliefs. This may be because Finnish teachers work in a context that provides high professional autonomy and agency (Niemi, 2015c), while the highly competitive admission to teacher education and its research-based character (Jakku-Sihvonen & Niemi, 2006) empowers Finnish pre-service teachers for independent decision-making.

However, teachers' futures thinking varied across European educational contexts, year of study, and teaching experiences. Lower-grade European pre-service teachers often have positive expectations about their futures as a teacher, and as they advance in their studies, increased academic pressure and a more realistic view of the profession may partly influence their visions. In addition, teachers with teaching experience demonstrated more concrete ideas about the future, as well as higher levels of capability to see different alternatives and opportunities for professional agency.

Findings from the qualitative narrative inquiry indicated that pre-service teachers explore the future of the teaching profession through broad perspectives and altering lenses, while also sharing common themes and areas of interest. Teacher's Sense of Responsibility manifested as the least future-oriented dimension in that the matters of responsibility, such as care for

equity and wellbeing, remained very close to those of the teachers' role today. Teacher's Openness to Futures were contemplated through uncertainty and hope, considering alternatives to how teaching is today but also to what teaching was like in their future narratives. While seldom clearly attributed to personal action, pre-service teachers associated Teacher's Agency Beliefs with the responsibility and power to create change, both among teachers as well as among broader society and political actors. Teacher's Systemic Awareness was considered through reflections on the role of the teacher and the school in society and change, beginning to ponder systems of change as a way to step closer to their desired futures.

The importance of understanding the role of various futures thinking activities in bringing different perspectives to light must also be highlighted. As portrayed in Fig. 1, Systemic Awareness and Agency Beliefs were manifested only minimally in the futures visioning task, but substantially more in the backcasting task. This reveals the crucial nature of building on creative futures thinking activities with tasks that delve deeper into the subject and challenge assumptions. Only by elaborating on the initial future vision through backcasting were pre-service teachers able to reflect on and understand systems of change and the actors, themselves included, behind them.

5.2 Implications

The quantitative and qualitative findings have several implications for the teaching profession, teacher education, and research thereon. The implications of the research reported here, supported by earlier research findings, are presented in the recent White Paper of the *teff* project (Laherto et al., 2026). Here we summarise some key implications.

First, since the difficulty of thinking about the future varied remarkably among the participants, broadening teachers' vision of educational futures is essential. Research has shown that teachers find it difficult to imagine multiple futures, especially versions of the future which are far from current trends, or desirable versions that reveal their values (Varpanen et al., 2022; Hyyppä et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2026). Activities such as backcasting, group discussions, use of various futures thinking techniques, and discussion of uncertainties (Laherto et al., 2026) can be achieved to foster future-oriented pre- and in-service teachers. Thus, the integration of futures thinking in teacher education is important. Teacher education should address the necessary capabilities of future-orientedness formally. This can manifest as integration of futures thinking as a pervasive theme in teacher education, a specific futures education course, future-oriented sustainability education, and promoting interdisciplinary education (Laherto et al., 2026). To support teacher's agency, teacher education should support disconnecting from predetermined conceptions of the future. Backcasting activities coupled with discussion of values and multiple educational futures can be effective in broadening pre-service teachers' futures thinking (Laherto et al., 2026).

The TFC dimensions manifested differently across different educational contexts. This suggests that in the actual practice of future-oriented teacher education, a single standard should be avoided. Instead, relevant interventions should be adjusted appropriately to different cultural backgrounds to enhance their applicability. On the other hand, providing opportunities for pre-service and in-service teachers from different European countries to

interact and have dialogues with each other can develop their understandings of various existing cultural and context-specific standards.

Finally, as futures thinking is a fundamental component of transformative agency (Laherto & Rasa, 2022; Varpanen et al., 2022), increasing comprehensive understanding of teachers' futures thinking from multiple levels and perspectives is necessary. The futures thinking instruments presented in this study can be useful for schools, administrators, policymakers, educators, researchers, and teachers themselves. An understanding of the underlying mechanisms of the teachers' futures thinking paves the way for the research-based development of future-oriented teacher education and professional development.

6. References

- Ahvenharju, S., Minkkinen, M., & Lalot, F. (2018). The five dimensions of Futures Consciousness. *Futures*, 104, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2018.06.010>
- Ahvenharju, S., Lalot, F., Minkkinen, M., & Quiamzade, A. (2021). Individual futures consciousness: Psychology behind the five-dimensional Futures Consciousness scale. *Futures*, 128, 102708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2021.102708>
- Cohen, J. (2013). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203771587>
- Cronbach, L. J. (1951). Coefficient Alpha and the internal structure of tests. *Psychometrika*, 16(3), 297–334. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02310555>
- Eren, A. (2012). Prospective Teachers' Interest in Teaching, Professional Plans about Teaching and Career Choice Satisfaction: A Relevant Framework? *Australian Journal of Education*, 56(3), 303–318. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000494411205600308>
- Hyypä, I., Rasa, T., & Laherto, A. (2024). Fostering students' systems thinking through futures education. *Frontline Learning Research*, 12(2), 27–50. <https://doi.org/10.14786/flr.v12i2.1301>
- Hyypä, I., Södervik, I., Krzywacki, H., & Laherto, A. (2025). Visioning Schooling in 2050: Analyzing Pre-Service Teachers' Futures Consciousness. In A. Rajala, A. Cortez, R. Hofmann, A. Jornet, H. Lotz-Sisitka, & L. Markauskaite (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference of the Learning Sciences - ICLS 2025*. (pp. 2095-2099). (ICLS Proceedings). ISLS International Society of the Learning Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.22318/icls2025.791591>
- Hyypä, I., Södervik, I., Krzywacki, H., Zhang, X., Rasa, T., & Laherto, A. (2026). Challenge your futures thinking - An introductory activity on futures thinking for teachers. In *(Re)Imagining Teacher Education in Times of Change: Empowering Future Teachers through Future Skills: Perspectives from the Erasmus+ Teacher Academy teff*
- Jakku-Sihvonen, R., & Niemi, H. (Eds.) (2006). *Research-based teacher education in Finland - reflections by Finnish teacher educators*. (Kasvatusalan tutkimuksia; No. 25). Finnish Educational Research Association.
- Kline, R. B. (2023). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling*. Guilford publications.
- Laherto, A., Södervik, I., Zhang, X., Hyypä, I., Krzywacki, H., Soroshzadeh, A., & Springob, J. (2026). *Teachers as Drivers of Change? Recommendations for Future-oriented Teacher Education (White paper)*. Erasmus+ Teacher Academy “Teacher Education for a Future in Flux” (teff). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19615523>

- Lombardo, T. (2014). The Future Evolution of Consciousness. *World Futures Review*, 6(3), 322–335. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1946756714552135>
- Lutovac, S., & Kaasila, R. (2014). Pre-service teachers' future-oriented mathematical identity work. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 85, 129–142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-013-9500-8>
- MacCallum, R. C., Browne, M. W., & Sugawara, H. M. (1996). Power analysis and determination of sample size for covariance structure modeling. *Psychological Methods*, 1(2), 130–149. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1082-989x.1.2.130>
- Miller, R. (2015). Learning, the Future, and Complexity. An essay on the emergence of Futures Literacy. *European Journal of Education*, 50(4), 513–523. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12157>
- Miller, R. (2018). *Transforming the Future (Open Access)*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351048002>
- Muthén, L. K., & Muthén, B. O. (1998–2023). *Mplus User's Guide* (8th ed.). Los Angeles, CA: Muthén & Muthén.
- Niemi, H. (2015c). Teacher professional development in Finland: Towards a more holistic approach. *Psychology Society & Education*, 7(3), 279. <https://doi.org/10.25115/psye.v7i3.519>
- O'Connor, K. E. (2008). "You choose to care": Teachers, emotions and professional identity. *Teaching and teacher education*, 24(1), 117-126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2006.11.008>
- OECD. (2019). *OECD future of education and skills 2030: OECD learning compass 2030 – A series of concept notes*. OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/>
- Poli, R. (2021). The challenges of futures literacy. *Futures*, 132, 102800. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2021.102800>
- Rasa, T., Lavonen, J., & Laherto, A. (2024). Agency and Transformative Potential of Technology in Students' Images of the Future. *Science & Education*, 33(5), 1145–1169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11191-023-00432-9>
- Sund, P., & Wickman, P. (2008). Teachers' objects of responsibility: something to care about in education for sustainable development? *Environmental Education Research*, 14(2), 145–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504620801951681>
- UNESCO (2021). *Reimagining our futures together: A new social contract for education*. Paris: UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379707>
- van Tartwijk, J. W. F., Zwart, R. C., & Wubbels, T. (2017). Developing teachers' competences with the focus on adaptive expertise in teaching. In D. J. Clandinin, & J. Husu (Eds.), *The SAGE Handbook of Research on Teacher Education* (pp. 820-835). SAGE. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781529716627>
- Varpanen, J., Laherto, A., Hilppö, J. & Ukkonen-Mikkola, T. (2022). Teacher agency and futures thinking. *Education Sciences*, 12(3), 177. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12030177>
- Vidergor, H. E. (2023). Teaching futures thinking literacy and futures studies in schools. *Futures*, 146, 103083. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2022.103083>
- Voogt, J., & Roblin, N. P. (2012). A comparative analysis of international frameworks for 21st century competences: Implications for national curriculum policies. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 44(3), 299–321. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2012.668938>
- Voros, J. (2003). A generic foresight process framework. *Foresight*, 5(3), 10–21. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14636680310698379>
- Zhang, X., Laherto, A., Hyyppä, I. M., Krzywacki, H., Tikkanen, L., & Södervik, I. (2026). Contextualization and Validation of the Futures Consciousness scale in Teacher Education. [Manuscript in preparation]